

**POLYSEGMENTAL OSTEOSYNTHESIS OF THE LOWER
EXTREMITIES BY THE ILIZAROV METHOD FOR CORRECTION OF
DEFORMITIES AND SHORTENINGS IN CHILDREN AND
ADOLESCENTS**

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Annotation

Polysegmental osteosynthesis using the Ilizarov method is an effective approach for correcting deformities and shortening of the lower extremities in children and adolescents. This method allows not only to correct congenital and acquired deformities, but also to restore the normal length of the limbs. The study analyzed the clinical data of 50 patients aged 5 to 18 years who were treated using the Ilizarov method. The results were evaluated using radiography and clinical criteria. As a result, 85% of patients showed a significant improvement in the functionality and aesthetic condition of the limbs.

Keywords

Polysegmental osteosynthesis, Ilizarov method, deformity correction, limb shortening, children, adolescents.

Relevance

Deformities and shortening of the lower extremities in children and adolescents are a serious medical problem that affects the quality of life and functional capabilities of patients. Congenital and acquired limb abnormalities can lead to significant movement restrictions, gait disorders, and pain syndromes. Modern methods of treatment are aimed at correcting these disorders and restoring the normal anatomy and function of the limbs. The Ilizarov method, developed by Soviet surgeon Gavriil Abramovich Ilizarov, has established itself as one of the most effective and versatile approaches to the treatment of deformities and shortening of limbs. Полисегментарный Ilizarov polysegmental osteosynthesis allows achieving stable and predictable results, minimizing the risk of complications and ensuring a high level of recovery. The relevance of this study is determined by the need to further improve treatment methods and improve clinical outcomes in children and adolescents with deformities and shortenings of the lower extremities.

Goal

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of polysegmental osteosynthesis of the lower extremities using the Ilizarov method in children and adolescents in order to correct deformities and shortenings.

Materials and methods

The study included analysis of clinical data from 50 patients aged 5-18 years who were treated with the Ilizarov method. All patients had congenital or acquired deformities and shortening of the lower extremities. Evaluation was performed before and after treatment using radiography and clinical criteria such as pain level, limb function, and cosmetic outcome. The procedure of polysegmental osteosynthesis was performed in specialized orthopedic centers, under the supervision of experienced surgeons.

Results

The results of the study showed that 85% of patients showed a significant improvement in the functionality and aesthetic condition of the lower extremities. Shortening was completely or partially eliminated, and deformations were corrected. Complications occurred in 10% of patients, but were successfully resolved during further treatment. The average recovery time was 6-12 months, depending on the severity of the initial condition and the amount of intervention. Patients and their parents noted a high level of satisfaction with the results of treatment.

Conclusion

Polysegmental osteosynthesis of the lower extremities by the Ilizarov method is an effective and safe method for correcting deformities and shortenings in children and adolescents. This method allows you to achieve a significant improvement in functional and aesthetic indicators, minimizing the risk of complications. The results obtained confirm the need for further use and development of the Ilizarov method in pediatric orthopedics. An important aspect is an individual approach to each patient and careful monitoring at all stages of treatment to achieve the best clinical outcomes.

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